

The Determinants of Entrepreneurial Success of Home-Based Entrepreneurs (HBEs) in Oman

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of the study was to analyze the impact of technology factors on the Success of home-based enterprises; to analyze the impact of marketing factors on the Success of home-based enterprises and to analyze the impact of environmental factors on the Success of home-based enterprises.

Design/methodology/approach: A structured questionnaire was provided to 208 participants for data collection selected on a stratified random sampling basis. The entrepreneurs from the North Al Batinah region in Oman including housewives and entrepreneurs operating from home were used for the study. The data was analyzed using SPSS.

Findings: The study revealed that there was an association between Environmental Factors, Marketing Factors, and the Success of home-based entrepreneurs. Environmental Factors and Marketing Factors had an impact on the Success of home-based entrepreneurs. But Technological factors - have not influenced the Success of home-based entrepreneurs.

Research limitations/implications: The paper will help home-based entrepreneurs to understand that the business from home as it is a form of local business entity necessary for community development and there is an incentive for small and medium business entities to educate the business process for the sustainability of their business.

Social Implications: Government should encourage home-based businesses as they are considered the legitimate form of HBEs for the sake of community development. Government should support channelizing the promotion and selling of business products for home-based businesses. Government should motivate the HBEs towards educating the business process for the sustainability of their businesses.

Originality / Value: This is the first kind of study dealing with the factors related to home-based entrepreneurs impacting the success of home-based entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Technological Factors, Marketing Factors, Environment Factors, Success of Home-based Business Factors, Barriers of Home-Based Entrepreneurs.

Introduction

Oman has experienced fast economic expansion since the discovery of crude oil. Oman, like other GCC countries, has had a favorable climate for corporate development and expansion over the last two decades. Oman's economic and social changes have aided the development of entrepreneurship efforts greatly. One of the goals of Oman's economic vision 2040 is to diversify the economy and provide job opportunities for young Omani citizens.

With fewer job opportunities in government jobs and private companies, the unemployment rate is high in the Sultanate of Oman. The unemployment rate has increased to 5 percent in 2020 from 1.80 percent in 2019 ([Trading Economics Global Macro Models Analysts](#), 2022). Entrepreneurship & self-employment can be the optimal solutions to overcome the problem of unemployment ([Bashir et al.](#), 2011; [Green](#), 2013). Home-Based entrepreneurship is one such process of setting up businesses in creating job opportunities. Indeed, it induces self-employment along with financial benefits. Even though the home-based businesses (HBBs) might be either professional or non-skilled, most of the HBBs in Oman are non-professional HBBs. Some of the examples of HBB in Oman are Omani sweets preparing & selling, Henna engraving, Private tutoring, Flower nursery, Gift basket designing, Drawing and painting, Weaving baskets, Embroidery, and Traditional Food preparation, Women clothes designing, Truckers, Software Trainers, etc.

Over the last decade, many rural and urban populations have turned to home-based self-employment to support themselves and their families. Modern technology in the form of the internet has helped Home-based Entrepreneurs (HBEs) to run/manage their businesses easily initiating their transactions from home offices ([Wilson & Mitchell](#), 2004). Further, it is not difficult to outsource most of the functions such as logistics, packaging, etc., but it is a must for an HBE to understand the factors that contribute to the success of home-based enterprises (HBENs). The main advantages of HBB are lower overhead, no need for commuting, the flexibility of work hours, space for family time, income tax advantages, etc. ([Ward](#), 2021). However, some of the HBEs might feel that they are isolated and out of the business community loop. HBBs are usually small businesses but mostly with zero employees. It does not mean that only one person is handling the business but they might be having part-time employees.

The identity of HBBs is based on the originality of such enterprises. Retaining its originality, development, and keeping pace with the changes in the world of commerce are the constraints faced by HBEs in the progress of such HBBs' improvement initiatives. The most important challenges are the lack of skills and experience of the HBEs besides financial barriers ([Modarresi et al.](#), 2017). Further, the identification of appropriate technologies for their specific businesses, the lack of marketing skills, and the need for proper resources for the survival of the business are the main challenges faced by the HBEs ([Alshawaf](#), 2020).

For the goal of determining the impact of the factors of entrepreneurship on success, researchers have identified that entrepreneurs with high creative self-efficacy are more likely to succeed in their firms. They may not be able to change failure entirely into success, but they can make a big difference in their success. How should these determinants be addressed?

Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How did the technology factors affect the success of home-based entrepreneurs?
2. How did the marketing factors affect the success of the home-based entrepreneurs?
3. How did the environmental factors affect the success of the home-based entrepreneurs?

Research Objectives

1. To analyze the technological factors affecting the Success of home-based entrepreneurs.
2. To analyze the marketing factors affecting the Success of home-based entrepreneurs.
3. To analyze the environmental factors affecting the Success of home-based entrepreneurs.

Problem Statement

As HBBs are invisible, their economic significance is presumed to be negligible ([Mason et al.](#), 2011). Most of the HBBs are at the miniature level and they have restricted/limited manpower, difficulties in increasing the number of product output, market reachability, and difficulty in expansion and growth. Limited/no knowledge of the technological advancement and lack of introduction of technology, lack of guidance to promote and sell business products for business from home, may hinder their business growth and advancement. Further, these, environmental disturbances and complaints from the neighborhood and local community, might hinder carrying out HBBs from houses selling products from doorsteps. Besides, the non-encouragement by the Government does not consider HBBs as a legal form of business entity in the necessary community development. Especially there is no incentive or any such scheme to HBEs in educating the business process for the sustainability of their businesses. Therefore, it has become important to analyze the determinants of the success of HBEs and the factors hindering such successes.

Literature Review

Success home-based businesses

[Galloway & Kapasi](#) (2014) observed that the motivations of HBBs were to earn an additional income. Improved work-life balance is touted as the biggest advantage of HBBs ([Kapasi & Galloway](#), 2015). Individual HBB's actual growth and expansion is observed in terms of increased turnover and sales, staff numbers, product and service offerings, return on investment, and market share ([Breen & Karanasios](#), 2010).

Family cooperation in overcoming challenges, rationalization of sleep hours for the sake of business, and hiring temporary personnel during busy periods, were the factors that have a significant impact on the gross revenue and the success of HBBs ([Beale](#), 2004). [Bin Dahari et al.](#) (2019) claimed that the Saudi ministry of commerce and industry encourages local women to start their HBBs as it strongly believes they are the fastest-growing sector which yields an alternative source of home-based income contributing to the national economy.

HBB differs from business to business according to their needs and the growth possibilities. Most of the successful HBEs built their HBBs conveniently at their home as it seems to be a more prevalent site of business ([Vorley & Rodgers](#), 2014). Spatial dislocation is a characteristic of successful HBBs ([Mason et al.](#), 2011). For some of the HBEs, their homes seem to be the business location whereas for others HBB means a convenient location and for most others, HBB means only a registered business address, not a place of work ([Newbery & Bosworth](#), 2010). HBB convenes lifestyle flexibility and capacity to manage work and family obligations and women are mostly benefited than men as gender was not a deciding factor in the decision to start an HBB ([Walker et al.](#), 2008). The number of women-run-HBBs is increasing. Women who run HBBs seem to have fewer work-family conflicts but with low profits compared to non-HBBs as HBBs are the only realistic alternatives for women ([Loscocco & Smith-Hunter](#), 2004).

Technology Factors

People's daily lives have become easier with the broad adoption of information and communication technology in their living space for electronically working and shopping besides family life ([Loo & Wang](#), 2018). In the modern world, technology in the form of electronic communications has become an integral part of the businesses as internet serves as the primary channel for many businesses ([Walker et al.](#), 2003). HBB is considered a unified concept, notwithstanding its diversity, offering specific advantages for certain new businesses such as variations in technology utilization and knowledge capital. ([Kapasi & Galloway](#), 2019). Micro-businesses run from the comfort of one's own home benefitting greatly from the digital economy ([Philip & Williams](#), 2019). The increasing availability of internet trading platforms encourages people to trade on the internet ([Daniel et al.](#), 2015). Home-based online business initiatives are becoming more popular as they are based on the concept of mental mobility operations ([Di Domenico et al.](#), 2014). The sales growth of an HBB depends on the use of technology, the number of hours HBE works, and the members of the family who assist in running the business ([Al Roomi & Ibrahim](#), 2004).

Marketing Factors

Although an online HBB is simple to operate and requires low-cost effort, marketing specialists point out that HBEs need to access the right marketing tools to effectively sell their products ([Blombäck & Craig](#), 2014). HBB does not require more investment in structure or equipment but innovative marketing ideas for your are essential in getting the right customers for their businesses ([Breen](#), 2010). The intersections between communication trends and marketing thought to enhance the marketing strategy of HBBs ([Kiang et al.](#), 2000; [Kumar et al.](#), 2020). [Smith \(2019\)](#) studied the marketing strategies of HBBs and found that most of the HBBs have taken an effort to market their businesses on social media. [Nor & Khin](#) (2016) observed that the majority of the HBB customers are getting involved in HBB business through online commerce especially using social media.

The marketing strategy of HBBs is based on customer-focused channels especially using social media on how HBBs' human, social/multicultural, and marketing capitals are explored ([Thrassou et al.](#), 2018). To come out of the marketing challenges HBBs require a more comprehensive yet detailed approach to marketing strategies ([Hastings & Anwar](#), 2019). HBBs need to consider several criteria concerning marketing channel selection functions when making channel decisions ([Chiu et al.](#), 2006).

Environmental Factors

HBB operators indulge in an environment in which commercialization works in a trial-and-error pattern ([Van Gelderen et al.](#), 2008). The attraction of HBB is driven by its flexibility and work-life balance of an HBB and the most determining factor is the number of dependents ([Walker et al.](#), 2008). Because HBBs are run from home, the roles, dynamics, the values of the family unit in which they began, and in general family and business functions are linked ([Olson et al.](#), 2003). Focus on work and works prospects are less with HBBs rather than non-HBBs whereas profit and the time devoted to work are strongly based on the HBEs ([Rodríguez-Modroño](#), 2021). HBEs develop IT skills by self-learning and let more difficult tasks to others by sub-contracting ([Anwar & Daniel](#), 2017).

[Walker & Webster](#) (2004) claimed that most people are thinking that HBBs are extended hobbies and not considered serious businesses. [Owen & Winter \(1991\)](#) came up with suggestions for creating a conducive environment for HBBs as they have the potential to supplement as an alternative income and community development. HBBs operated by women are credible business models with substantial ambitions, which are mostly hobby related and have short lifespans ([Rowe et al.](#), 1999).

Figure 1 Theoretical Framework

Research Hypotheses

To determine the factors affecting the entrepreneurial success of HBBs in Oman, the considered independent variables are marketing factors, environmental factors, and technology factors, and the dependent variable is the success of HBEs.

Accordingly, the following hypotheses were defined:

- H1: There is a relationship between technology factors and the Success of home-based entrepreneurs.
- H2: There is a relationship between marketing factors and the Success of home-based entrepreneurs.
- H3: There is a relationship between the environmental factors and the Success of home-based entrepreneurs.

Research Methodology

Non-probability sampling was used in this study. A structured questionnaire was provided to 208 participants for data collection selected on a stratified random sampling basis. The entrepreneurs from the North Al Batinah region in Oman including housewives and entrepreneurs operating from home were selected for the study. To find out the relationship between the independent variable - marketing factors, environmental factors, technology factors, and the dependent variable - the success of home businesses, the data was analyzed using SPSS.

Table 1 Demographic Details

	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	38	18.3
	Female	170	81.7
Nationality	Omani	205	98.6
	Non-Omani	3	1.4
Marital Status	Single	104	50.0
	Married	78	37.5
	Engaged	16	7.7
	Divorced	10	4.8
Age	< 20 years	118	56.7
	> 20 & < 30 years	118	56.7
	> 30 & < 40 years	53	25.5
	> 40 & < 50 years	30	14.4
	50 years & above	7	3.4
Work Experience	< 5 years	108	51.9
	5 - < 10 years	62	29.8
	10 - < 15 years	25	12.0
	15 years & above	13	6.3
	< 5 years	108	51.9
Category	Housewives	52	25.0
	Job seekers	62	29.8
	Business pioneer	25	12.0
	Retired	12	5.8
	Other	57	27.4
Education	High school & Below	38	18.3
	Post-graduate	31	14.9
	Diploma	39	18.8
	Vocational courses	13	6.3
	Others	21	10.1

Source: Data Collected

Technological Factors

Table 2 Technological Factors

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	Chi-square	p-value
HBEs use smartphones to enhance their production process	19 9.1%	16 7.7%	29 13.9%	58 27.9%	86 41.3%	.184	319.894	.000
Technology helps to save the time of HBBs during processing and organizing	20 9.6%	15 7.2%	34 16.3%	95 45.7%	44 21.2%	.284		
Technology helps HBES to save working costs	21 10.1%	16 7.7%	27 13.0%	66 31.7%	78 37.5%	.234		

Raw materials can easily be ordered by HBEs through websites/smartphones	17 8.2%	19 9.1%	31 14.9%	86 41.3%	55 26.4%	.267		
Technology helps HBBs to explore more business opportunities	23 11.1%	12 5.8%	30 14.4%	76 36.5%	67 32.2%	.225		
With the help of technology, HBBs can increase their productivity	19 9.1%	17 8.2%	30 14.4%	86 41.3%	56 26.9%	.256		
Technology helps in the innovation and development of HBBs	23 11.1%	13 6.3%	25 12.0%	81 38.9%	66 31.7%	.227		
Technology helps to expand the HBBs to a global level	20 9.6%	16 7.7%	30 14.4%	65 31.3%	77 37.0%	.219		

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between the technological factors and the choices of the respondents.

From Table 2, it is clear that the p-value is less than .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected which means that there exists a relationship between the technological factors and the choices of the respondents. The K-S values obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it is observed that ‘Technology help to save the time of home-based businesses during processing and organizing’ (.284) ranks first among the choices, ‘Raw materials can easily be ordered by HBEs through websites/smartphones’ (.267) ranked second and ‘With the help of technology, home-based businesses can increase their productivity (.256) ranks third.

Marketing Factors

Table 3 Marketing Factors

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	Chi-square	p-value
Marketing factors were the main obstacles to the entrepreneurship development of HBBs	17 8.2%	13 6.3%	65 31.3%	66 31.7%	47 22.6%	.198	214.885	.000
Promotion and sales can be smoothly handled by HBEs	16 7.7%	16 7.7%	47 22.6%	94 45.2%	35 16.8%	.277		
Competitors’ strategies can be easily identified by HBEs	12 5.8%	17 8.2%	49 23.6%	68 32.7%	62 29.8%	.220		
Material suppliers were well organized and frequencies were easily estimated	14 6.7%	17 8.2%	46 22.1%	87 41.8%	44 21.2%	.262		
With a closely knitted production process, quality products can be processed	15 7.2%	12 5.8%	54 26.0%	75 36.1%	52 25.05	.229		
Customer orientation is easier in HBBs	15 7.2%	15 7.2%	49 23.6%	91 43.8%	38 18.3%	.268		
Customers can opine on the product quality if marketing is done through social media	16 7.7%	15 7.2%	40 19.2%	71 34.1%	66 31.7%	.241		
Promoting and marketing products are done at a low cost-effectively	20 9.6%	13 6.3%	39 18.8%	85 40.9%	51 27.5%	.271		

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between marketing factors and respondents’ choices.

From Table 3, it is clear that the p-value is less than .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected which means that there exists a relationship between the marketing factors and the choices of the respondents. The K-S values obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test are compared, and it is observed that ‘Promotion and sale can be smoothly handled by HBEs’ (.277) ranks first among the choices, ‘Promoting and marketing products are done at low cost effectively’ (.271) ranked second and ‘Customer orientation is easier in home-based businesses’ (.268) ranks third.

Environmental Factors

Table 4 Environmental Factors

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	Chi-square	p-value
HBEs sleep less and carry more tension than the other business owners	24 11.5%	15 7.2%	56 26.9%	60 28.8%	53 25.5%	.198	228.115	.000
Education leads to the success of HBBs	15 7.2%	14 6.7%	45 21.6%	88 42.3%	46 22.1%	.266		
Encouragement from family members and others made them work from home	18 8.7%	10 4.8%	47 22.6%	83 39.9%	50 24.0%	.256		
HBBs are usually considered hobby businesses/ short-time life	17 8.2%	21 10.1%	41 19.7%	86 41.3%	43 20.7%	.267		
Women-owned HBBs are a legitimate form of business with serious intentions	20 9.6%	9 4.3%	44 21.2%	83 39.9%	52 25.0%	.261		
HBBs are of a community development nature due to supplemental income nature	16 7.7%	16 7.7%	39 18.8%	81 38.9%	56 26.9%	.261		
The functioning of the family and that of the businesses are intertwined	16 7.7%	14 6.7%	52 25.0%	87 41.8%	39 18.8%	.256		
Social networks & technical aids at home enable them to become HBEs	15 7.2%	15 7.2%	46 22.1%	80 38.5%	52 25.0%	.249		

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between environmental factors and respondents’ choices.

From Table 4, it is clear that the p-value is less than .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected which means that there exists a relationship between the business environmental factors and the choices of the respondents. The K-S values obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test are compared, and it is observed that ‘Home-based businesses are usually considered as hobby businesses/ short-time life’ (.267) ranks first among the choices, ‘Education leads to the success of HBBs’ (.266) ranked second and ‘Women-owned HBBs are a legitimate form of businesses with serious intentions’ and ‘HBBs are of community development nature due to supplemental income nature’ (.261) ranks third.

Success of HBEs

Table 5 Success of HBEs

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	Chi-square	p-value
HBBs are successful as they involve little operation costs	19 9.1%	14 6.7%	62 29.8%	57 27.4%	56 26.9%	.184	243.452	.000
Managing is easier in HBBs due to a smaller number of workers	14 6.7%	17 8.2%	43 20.7%	96 46.2%	38 18.3%	.284		
The entry of new competitors triggers HBEs to respond quickly and effectively	17 8.2%	18 8.7%	46 22.1%	72 34.6%	55 26.4%	.234		
HBEs have more freedom to choose their business roles and business lifestyle	18 8.7%	15 7.2%	42 20.2%	86 41.3%	47 22.6%	.267		
HBBs have continuous growth	16 7.7%	13 6.3%	46 22.1%	80 38.5%	53 25.5%	.250		
HBBs make more profit	16 7.7%	15 7.2%	47 22.6%	84 40.4%	46 22.1%	.256		
Products by HBEs are more innovative and valuable	16 7.7%	16 7.7%	52 25.0%	73 35.1%	51 24.5%	.227		
HBEs achieve socially desirable and responsible outcomes	19 9.1%	10 4.8%	56 26.9%	70 33.7%	53 25.5%	.219		

Null Hypothesis: There is no link between the success of HBE factors and respondents' choices.

From Table 5, it is clear that the p-value is less than .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected which means that there exists a relationship between the success of HBE factors and the choices of the respondents. The K-S values obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test are compared, and it is observed that 'Managing is easier in HBBs due to a smaller number of workers' (.284) ranks first among the choices. 'HBEs have more freedom to choose their business roles and business lifestyle' (.267) ranked second and 'HBBs make more profit' (.256) ranks third.

Regression Analysis

Table 6 (a), (b), (c), and (d)

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
Environment Factors, Technological Factors, Marketing Factors, Success of HBEs	...	Enter

^aDependent Variable: Success of HBEs

^bAll requested variables entered.

Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.931 ^a	.867	.865	2.95046

Predictors: (Constant), Environment Factors, Technological Factors, Marketing Factors

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	11595.449	3	3865.150	444.005	.000 ^b
Residual	1775.859	204	8.705		
Total	13371.308	207			

^aDependent Variable: Success of HBEs

^bPredictors: (Constant), Environment Factors, Technological Factors, Marketing Factors

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	.367	.810		.453	.651
Environment Factors	.019	.045	.021	.421	.674
Technological Factors	.528	.068	.507	7.727	.000
Marketing Factors	.436	.071	.426	6.113	.000

^aDependent Variable: Success of HBEs

The p-value for Environmental Factors, Technology Factors, and Marketing Factors are > 0.05 Thus, eliminating the variable Technological factors and the regression analysis is carried out again and thus the new regression analysis results are as follows:

Table 7 (a), (b), (c) and (d)

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Environment Factors, Marketing Factors	...	Enter

^aDependent Variable: Success of HBEs

^bAll requested variables entered.

Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.931 ^a	.867	.865	2.95046

Predictors: (Constant), Environment Factors, Technological Factors, Marketing Factors

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	11593.908	2	5796.954	668.604	.000 ^b
Residual	1777.399	205	8.670		
Total	13371.308	207			

^aDependent Variable: Success of HBEs

^bPredictors: (Constant), Environment Factors, Marketing Factors

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	.363	.808		.449	.654
Marketing Factors	.535	.066	.514	8.111	.000
Environment Factors	.449	.065	.438	6.909	.000

^aDependent Variable: Success of HBEs

The obtained linear regression is:

$$SHbE = .363 + .535 \times M + .449 \times E$$

where M = Marketing Factors and E = Environment Factors.

It can be seen from the above table that the Success of HBEs is dependent on Marketing factors and Environment factors, i.e. both Marketing and Environment factors have an impact on the Success of HBEs. It is also found that there is no relationship between the Success of HBEs and Technological Factors.

Discussion

From the responses, it is observed that ‘Technology help to save the time of HBBs during processing and organizing’, ‘Raw materials can easily be ordered by HBEs through websites/smartphones’, and ‘With the help of technology, HBBs can increase their productivity’ are the most preferred choices of the respondents among the technological factors.

From the responses, it is observed that ‘Channels of promotion and sale can be handled smoothly by HBEs’, ‘Promoting and marketing family-made products are done at the lowest cost professionally and effectively’ and ‘Customer orientation is easier in home-based businesses’ are the most preferred choices of the respondents among the marketing factors.

From the responses, it is observed that ‘Home-based businesses are usually considered as hobby businesses and short-time life businesses’, ‘Education leads to the success of their home-based businesses’ and ‘Women-owned HBBs are considered to be a legitimate form of businesses with serious intentions’ and ‘Home-based businesses may be considered as a form of community development due to its supplemental income source nature’ are the most preferred choices of the respondents among the environmental factors.

From the responses, it is observed that ‘Management of workers is easier as home-based businesses involve the minimum number of employees’, ‘Home based business have more freedom to choose business roles and business life style’ and ‘Home based business help to make more profit’ are the most preferred choices of the respondents among the Success of HBE factors.

Further, it is also observed that there is an association between Marketing Factors, Environment Factors, and the success of home-based enterprises i.e., the Marketing Factors and Environmental Factors have an impact on the Success of HBEs. But Technological factors do not influence the Success of HBEs.

In other words, Marketing Factors and Environmental Factors influence the Success of HBBs i.e. Hypothesis No. 2 Marketing Factors have an influence on the Success of home-based entrepreneurs, i.e. Hypothesis No. 3 Environment Factors have an influence on the Success of home-based entrepreneurs are positively proved. All the factors did not influence the Success of home-based entrepreneurs. Only Environmental Factors and Marketing Factors influence the Success of home-based businesses, i.e. Hypothesis No. 1 was disproved.

Recommendations

Based on the following recommendations have been proposed:

- Government should encourage HBBs as they are considered the legitimate form of HBEs for the sake of community development due.
- Government should support channelizing the promotion and selling of business products for the HBBs.
- Government should motivate the HBEs towards educating the business process for the sustainability of their businesses.

Research Implications

we have found that it influences marketing and environmental factors in the success of entrepreneurs. Where this study confirms the importance of the influence of factors on the determinants of the success of HBEs and how they can help in the development and success of home-based entrepreneurship. Every entrepreneur should focus on the factors that can help in the success of his work, whether from home or anywhere else.

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